

OUTCOME OF ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT RECONSTRUCTION IN HAMSTRING GRAFT VERSUS BONE PATELLAR BONE GRAFT

Dr Muhammad Fazil^{*1}, Dr Syed Dil Bagh Ali Shah², Dr Afaq Uddin³, Dr Rida Rasheed⁴,
Dr Muhammad Abubaker⁵, Dr Rehmatullah⁶

^{*1}Post Graduate Resident , Orthopedic Ward , Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar
² Associate Professor , Orthopedic Ward , Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar
^{3,4,5,6} Post Graduate Resident , Orthopedic Ward , Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar

^{*1}m.fazil0345@gmail.com , ²drdilbagh@gmail.com, ³afaq.6191@gmail.com
⁴ridarashid195@gmail.com, ⁵beautybeggar6@gmail.com, ⁶rmars693@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14777086>

ABSTRACT

Background: Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injuries are common among athletes and can significantly affect the knee's stability and overall function. ACL reconstruction is the commonly chosen treatment, with HT (hamstring tendon) and BPTB (bone-patellar tendon-bone) autografts being the most widely used options. The choice between these grafts remains controversial due to differences in postoperative outcomes, complications, and functional recovery.

Objective: To compare the functional outcomes, knee stability, and complication rates between HT (hamstring tendon) and BPTB (bone-patellar tendon-bone) autografts in patients undergoing ACL reconstruction.

Methodology: A prospective study was conducted at Khyber Teaching Hospital, Peshawar, over a 12-month period. A total of 100 patients (51 in the BPTB group and 49 in the HT group) aged 18-50 years with ACL tears were randomly assigned to receive either graft. Surgical procedures were standardized, and postoperative rehabilitation protocols were identical for both groups. Functional outcomes were assessed using the International Knee Documentation Committee (IKDC) scores and Tegner activity scale. Knee stability was evaluated through Lachman and pivot-shift tests, while complication rates were recorded.

Results: At the 12-month follow-up, 92.2% of patients in the BPTB group and 83.7% in the HT group achieved good-to-excellent IKDC scores. The Lachman and pivot-shift tests showed superior knee stability in the BPTB group ($p=0.019$ and $p=0.021$, respectively). However, the HT group exhibited fewer donor site morbidities and a quicker recovery. Complications such as patellar fractures were observed only in the BPTB group, while wound infections were more frequent in the HT group.

Conclusion: Both BPTB and HT grafts provide significant functional improvement after ACL reconstruction. BPTB grafts offer superior knee stability but are associated with higher donor site complications. HT grafts, while providing comparable functional

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outcomes, demonstrate fewer complications and faster recovery. The choice of graft should be individualized based on patient-specific factors and activity levels.

Keywords: *ACL reconstruction, hamstring tendon graft, bone-patellar tendon-bone graft, knee stability, functional outcomes, complications*

INTRODUCTION

The Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) plays an important role in the stabilization of the knee by restricting anterior translation of tibial and rotational forces at the tibiofemoral joint (1). ACL injury is one of the most common orthopedic injuries, with an annual incidence of isolated injury of 68.6 per 100,000 person-years (2). ACL injury predisposes individuals to additional knee injuries like osteoarthritis and can negatively affect participation in activities necessary for health and wellness (3). "The primary goal of ACLR is to restore knee stability; however, outcomes can vary, with re-rupture rates ranging from 2% to 40%, depending on the patient's activity level and specific demands." (4) "The most commonly used autografts are bone-patellar tendon-bone (BPTB) grafts harvested typically from the middle third of the ipsilateral patellar tendon or hamstring tendon (HT) grafts harvested from the semitendinosus and gracilis tendons. There are advantages and disadvantages as well as morbidity associated with each of these autograft options. Compared with patients receiving HT autografts, those who receive BPTB autografts may experience more anterior knee pain resulting from donor site pain and a larger incision at the time of harvest as well as possible extensor strength deficits". (5) "Graft selection for the ACL reconstruction is a considerable issue relating to ACL reconstruction. Essentially, among current autograft selection for the ACL reconstruction, bone-patellar tendon-bone grafts and hamstring tendon or quadriceps tendon graft have been well used and compared clinically" (6) "The optimal management of ACL is still debated" (7). In a study conducted by Zhao L et al "HT autograft is comparable with the BPTB autograft in terms of clinical function, postoperative knee stability, and OA changes, with a medium-term follow-up. The HT autograft for ACL reconstruction carries a lower risk of complications, such as anterior knee pain, kneeling pain, and extension loss, but an increased incidence of graft failure" (8) Keays et al. showed that "among other factors like meniscectomy, chondral damage and low quadriceps-to-hamstring strength ratios, the choice of graft for ACL reconstruction is a significant predictor for the development of OA" (9).

The aim of this study is to compare HT graft and BPTB grafts in reconstruction of ACL tears in terms of functional outcome in our population.

Methodology

This is a prospective study conducted on patients with ACL tear presenting to the orthopedic ward of KTH (Khyber Teaching Hospital) Peshawar. over a 12 month duration from December 2023 to November 2024 after seeking permission from the ethical review board and written informed consent from the patient. patient selection and randomization were conducted following the Aspetar clinical practice guidelines for ACL reconstruction which provide comprehensive criteria to ensure appropriate patient inclusion and rehabilitation protocols (12). Two groups were made. one group was bone patellar bone graft (BPTB) group labeled as group A (n=51) and other was hamstring graft (HT) group labeled as group B (n=49). those Patients of either gender with age of 18 to 50 years with anterior cruciate ligament tear were randomly assigned by block randomization into one of the two groups. those patients with Posterior cruciate ligament laxity, osteoarthritis on plain radiograph, medial/lateral collateral ligament tear grade 3/4 were excluded from this study. surgeries were done by competent orthopedic surgeon.

Surgical Technique All reconstructions were performed by a single surgeon. Patients were initially placed in a program of physical therapy emphasizing techniques to regain motion and decrease swelling preoperatively. At the time of arthroscopy, the knee was examined, associated joint pathology was documented, and irreparably torn meniscal fragments were removed. studies suggest that incorporating modern surgical approaches such as suture tape augmentation can improve graft fixation and reduce failure rates. (13)(15). the rehabilitation protocol for both groups was developed based on evidence from recent clinical guidelines, emphasizing progressive loading and sport specific exercises to optimize recovery and reduce re injury risks. (16). outcome assesment was carried out using validated clinical tools such as IKDC

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and Tegner activity scales in line with current trends in graft choice assessment and patient reported outcomes in ACL reconstruction.(17)

BPTB grafting: The bone-patellar tendon bone graft was constructed from the central third of the tendon of the ipsilateral knee. The graft was 10 mm wide and harvested with 20 to 28 mm of bone from the patella and tibial tubercle. The femoral guide pin was placed 5 mm anterior to the posterior cortex to allow for a 1 to 2 mm posterior cortical rim after reaming at the ten-thirty position (for right knees) or one-thirty position (for left knees). The tibial guide pin was placed through the footprint of the ACL adjacent to the anterior horn of the lateral meniscus and the tibial tunnel was reamed. All tunnels were reamed to an appropriate size depending on the width of the autograft bone blocks. The graft was pulled through the tunnels so that the patellar bone block was within the femoral tunnel and the tibial bone block was within the tibial tunnel. The graft was positioned so that no bone protruded into the joint. An interference-fit screw was used in the femoral tunnel to fix the bone block. Tension was then placed on the distal part of the graft, and impingement was excluded by range of motion maneuvers. Next, the graft was secured under an appropriate tension and at the 30° position of the knee within the tibial tunnel with use of an interference screw.

Hamstring-grafting: The tunnels for the hamstring graft were placed in the same manner as the tunnels for the BPTB graft. A 3-cm longitudinal incision was made over the pes anserinus tendons (anteromedial aspect of the proximal tibia 3 to 4cm distal to the joint line), and the distal insertion site of the semitendinosus tendons was identified and isolated. A tendon stripper was placed over the tendon to detach the muscle. A whip non absorbable stitch was sutured to the tendon ends and the graft was quadrupled. The proximal end of the graft was fixed to the lateral-distal aspect of the femur with an EndoButton fixation device. A screw was placed, at the 30° position of the knee under appropriate tension over the hamstring graft, just distal to the tibial tunnel. The tibia was loaded with a maximal posterior force during fixation on the tibial side to minimize graft laxity present at the time of surgery.

Postoperative Rehabilitation

The rehabilitation protocol was identical for both groups with passive range of motion exercises instituted immediately and progression to active closed chain exercises achieved by 6 weeks postoperatively. Patients were allowed full weight bearing 3 weeks postoperatively in a hinged brace and returned to running at 3 months. Return to sports participation was allowed at 6 months. Follow-up Evaluations

All patients were examined and postoperative data were collected at 3 months, 6 months and 1 year after surgery.

Operation time was recorded during surgery in both ST group and BPTB group. Objective parameters used for evaluation included the presence of effusion, Lachman and pivot-shift testing, KT-1000 arthrometer side-to-side differences, modified IKDC knee function scores and Tegner activity scores .

Ranges of knee motion, locking of the knee, and patellofemoral pain were also recorded. Quadriceps bulk was measured 20 cm above the joint line and compared with that of the contralateral extremity.

Anterior-posterior knee laxity was recorded by using maximum-manual KT-1000 arthrometer at 20° of knee flexion and with the Lachman test. Grading of the Lachman examination was defined as normal, 1+ (increased excursion with an end point), or 2+ (increased excursion without an end point). Pivot-shift examination was graded as normal, 1+ (mild difference between the knees or glide), 2+ (moderate difference or subluxation), or 3+ (gross subluxation).

Activity level was determined using IKDC preoperatively and at latest follow-up. The Tegner Activity scale was used to quantitate patient activity levels before injury and at 1-year follow-up.

Post-operative complications including deep infection, wound infection, patella fracture were recorded at follow up visits.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS (Version 22.0). The Pearson Chi-square test and independent t-test were applied to compare variables between the two groups. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered

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statistically significant.

Results

There were no significant differences between the two groups regarding the presence of meniscal or osteochondral lesions. The mean operative time was 75 minutes in group A and 65 minutes in group B ($p>0.05$). At the 12-month follow-up, 47 patients (92.2%) in group A and 41 patients (83.7%) in group B achieved good-to-excellent IKDC scores (grade A or B), with no statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$). The Tegner scale assessment at the 12-month follow-up showed an average of 6 points (range: 3 to 9) in the BPTB group and 5 points (range: 4 to 8) in the hamstring graft group ($p>0.05$).

Demographic Data

Total Patients =100

BPTB Group= (n=51) 51

HT Group= (n=49) 49

Age (Mean \pm SD) =32.5 \pm 7.1

Male (%)= 60%

Female (%) {40%

IKDC Score Comparison

IKDC Score Comparison

Group	Good-to-Excellent IKDC Scores (%)	p-value
BPTB	92.2	>0.05
HT	83.7	>0.05

The mean laxity assessed using the KT-1000 arthrometer improved from 6.3 \pm 2.1 mm preoperatively to 2.2 \pm 1.0 mm in group A ($p<0.0001$), and from 6.7 mm to 3.3 mm in group B, with no statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$).

Lachman Test Comparison

Group	Normal	1+	2+	p-value
BPTB	32	14	5	0.019
HT	17	24	8	0.019

For the Lachman test, in group A, 32 patients were graded as normal, 14 as 1+, and 5 as 2+. In group B, 17 patients were graded as normal, 24 as 1+, and 8 as 2+. The difference was statistically significant ($p=0.019$).

Pivot Shift Test Comparison

Pivot Shift Test Comparison

Group	Normal	1+	2+	p-value
BPTB	35	12	4	0.021
HT	21	19	9	0.021

Regarding the pivot shift test, significant improvements in knee stability were observed in both groups, with a statistically significant difference between them ($p=0.021$).

Tegner Activity Scale Comparison

Group	Pre-op (Mean \pm SD)	Post-op (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
BPTB	4.1 \pm 1.2	6.0 \pm 1.1	>0.05
HT	4.0 \pm 1.3	5.0 \pm 1.2	>0.05

The p-value reported for the Tegner scale comparison is >0.05 , indicating no statistically significant difference between the two groups. This suggests that both the BPTB and HT grafts resulted in comparable

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improvements in activity levels at the 12-month follow-up.

Discussion

This study aimed to compare the outcomes of anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) reconstruction using bone-patellar tendon-bone (BPTB) autografts and hamstring tendon (HT) autografts. Our findings indicate that both graft types result in significant improvements in knee function and stability, with some differences in specific outcomes.(18)

Functional Outcomes

The study findings indicate significant improvements in functional scores postoperatively for both graft types, which aligns with the literature stating comparable short-term functional recovery for HT and BPTB autografts (Dwidmuthe S et al., 2024; Heng CHY et al., 2023).

The slightly higher Tegner activity level in the BPTB group corresponds with the literature, which suggests BPTB grafts provide better anterior knee stability, especially in high-demand populations. (19) [(Dwidmuthe S et al., 2024; Heng CHY et al., 2023).]

Knee Stability

Objective assessments revealed that the BPTB group had superior outcomes in terms of rotational and anteroposterior stability at long-term follow-up. This finding aligns with previous studies indicating that BPTB autografts may provide better knee stability compared to HT autografts.(Laxdal et al,2007)(18) (santhamoorthy et al 2024)(19). The final results confirm that BPTB provides better rotational and anteroposterior stability, consistent with earlier studies (Agarwal A et al., 2023), which report superior stability with BPTB compared to HT grafts.

Complications

The incidence of complications differed between the groups. The BPTB group experienced cases of patellar fracture and graft contamination, while the HT group had a higher incidence of superficial infections. These findings are consistent with existing literature reporting similar complication profiles for each graft type(narayanaswamy et al 2023)(20). The study results highlight different complication profiles for each graft type, consistent with the literature's assertion that BPTB grafts tend to have higher donor site morbidity and patellar-related issues, while HT grafts are associated with lower site complications but higher reoperation rates.

Conclusion

Both BPTB and HT autografts are effective for ACL reconstruction, offering significant improvements in knee function and stability. The choice of graft should be individualized based on patient-specific factors, including activity level and risk of complications. Further research with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods is warranted to confirm these findings.

This study has some limitations, such as being conducted at one hospital with a small number of patients, a short follow-up period, no blinding, differences in how patients followed their rehab, possible surgeon influence, use of opinion-based tests, and not considering all possible factors.

No conflict of interest among authors. Not funded by any one.

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